

ABOUT THE MEANINGFUL STRUCTURE OF THE SENTENCE*R. Kurbonova*¹*Abstract:*

In most cases, when thinking about linguistic signs, the existing views about the unity of form and content in them—in other words, about expressive and expressive aspects—are meant. From this point of view, looking at the sentence as a linguistic sign, and even more so, the cases of finding, separating the form and content, expressive and expressive components, and expressing an opinion about them have become widespread. In the same way that the units that appear as linguistic units but have communicative-significant properties other than nominative-denotative properties are recorded as predicative units, specific opinions are expressed about their propositional structure. According to this basis, the sentence was noted as the most minimal of the speech derivative constructions, and important views related to the definition of its structural, semantic, and pragmatic features were put forward.

Key words: clause, sentence, proposition, presupposition, word, language, speech, language and speech units, theme-rhema, structural, semantic, and pragmatic factors.

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While studying the views in this regard, first of all, we note that it is necessary to separate the concept of the sentence and its different aspects from other linguistic signs based on a unique approach. It can be noted that great attention and efforts to study these issues have intensified since the sixties of the last century.

N.D. Arutyunova suggested that the sentence can be checked from form to content or from content to form, while N.Y. Shvedova notes that the main task of syntactic semantics should be to determine the specific meanings of formal-syntactic models. In this opinion, the general meaning of the structure of the sentence and the relationship between them serve as the basis of the syntactic structure of the sentence. In addition, opinions were expressed about the fact that the nominative minimum of the sentence should be based on the lexical meanings of the members, the meaningful structure of the sentence should be separated not within the limits of the structural schemes, but outside the generality, and the structural scheme and the meaningful structures should be located in parallel lines that do not intersect with each other. Such reasoning O.I. Moskalskaya, E.P. The views of linguists like Paducheva take precedence.

That is why the content structure of any sentence is complex and multifaceted, and does not require proof. The mentioned points make it possible to justify that the overall meaning, content and functional value of the sentence is derived from the unity of the propositivity, modality and communicative properties of the sentence.

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It can be noted that the syntactic device described in linguistics by the term sentence is a minimal syntactic device, at the same time it is a minimal speech device, the smallest unit of speech. The most important of the above three members that make up the substantive structure of this unit is the propositional structure that reflects certain situations or events in objective existence. In this respect, it is correct and reasonable to understand simple sentences as a monopropositive syntactic device. Viewing the proposition as a linguistic expression of the real existence reflected in the human mind allows to describe and describe the true essence of this concept in today's linguistics, when it is measured by the criteria of today's development of linguistics.

While thinking about the propositional aspect of sentence semantics, first of all, we would like to mention that its propositional aspect refers to the perceptions of its monopropositive character. In addition, the modality and communicative aspects of speech are also important, and they are directly related to the concept of personality. It will not be possible to study these two aspects in depth and fully, which are mentioned in the study of speech as a linguistic unit.

From what we have mentioned, only propositional and objective modality features of the sentence as a language unit are manifested in the semantics of the sentence. However, if we consider the sentence as a unit of speech in the literal sense, then the range of its semantic properties includes communicative properties and, in turn, signs of subjective modality. Of course, extralinguistic factors also play a role in the content of the sentence. It cannot be denied. The linguistic world of a person and the related linguistic activity do not fully reflect the real existence. Therefore, even if different people understand a certain situation in a general way, even if they try to convey the essence close to each other, there will be no absolute uniformity. When it comes to such situations, in the work of A. Nurmonov, N. Makhmudov, A. Akhmedov, S. Soliho'jayeva "The meaningful syntax of the Uzbek language", some linguists, while not rejecting the extralinguistic factor outside the language in the content of the sentence, the objective existence of the language expression, not directly with the situation, but based on the connection through the "images of objective existence" existing in the human mind, they used the term "situation" to refer to the mental situation located in the mental space and mental time.

We support the above opinions in this regard, and we consider A. Vejbitskaya's views on the same issue to be appropriate. According to him, the subject of semantics is not real existence, but the expression of this real existence in the human mind. The reason for such an opinion is that, according to him, language can express objective existence only through consciousness. In fact, the formation of a concrete sentence requires a multi-stage process. If the starting point of its formation is to determine the meaningful similarities that express the denotative-referential meaning, the next process will certainly take place with the increase of communicative features.

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